

Reproduce experimental results: Implicit Session Contexts for Next-Item Recommendations

188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science 2023W | Exercise 2

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This document represents our endeavor to reproduce and extend the results of the original research named Implicit Session Contexts for Next-Item Recommendations [1]. Acknowledging the collaborative spirit of the original authors, we utilized the provided GitHub link, which included both the code and datasets. It's important to note that, despite the availability of these resources, comprehensive documentation was not provided by the original authors.

During our experiments, we faced challenges due to limited computing resources when running the code on the four datasets. As we worked on the experiments, we spent a significant amount of time dealing with issues in the stellargraph library, which caused hiccups in our experiments. After some research, we found a solution by downgrading the Python version, allowing us to proceed with our tests. All of the results will be further explained in addition.

CCS CONCEPTS: Information systems → Recommender systems

KEYWORDS: Session-based Recommendation, Session Contextualization

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1 INTRODUCTION

"Implicit Session Contexts for Next-Item Recommendations" [1] introduces ISCON, a novel approach designed to enhance the accuracy of next-item predictions in session-based recommender systems. The paper addresses the limitations of existing context-aware models in session-based recommender systems, particularly in scenarios where session context information is not explicitly given or needs to be implicitly inferred. ISCON aims to overcome these limitations by introducing a method to assign precise and meaningful implicit contexts to sessions.

1.1 Proposed Approach: ISCON

The ISCON model consists of three main components aimed at enhancing next-item prediction accuracy through session context contextualization and utilization:

- **Session Contextualization:** This involves generating session embeddings from a user-item multigraph and clustering sessions to identify session context clusters. Session embeddings are obtained using GraphSage applied to a bipartite multigraph. Clustering sessions helps identify similar sessions with the same implicit context.
- **Session Context Prediction:** Predicting the context of future sessions in real-time is crucial. ISCON utilizes short-term and long-term interest vectors along with a trainable user embedding. Bidirectional LSTMs are trained to capture both short-term and long-term user interests.
- **Next-Item Predictions with Session Contexts:** ISCON utilizes predicted session context embeddings, item-level interest, and user embedding for personalization in generating next-item recommendations. It concatenates predicted session context embeddings with item-level interest and user embeddings, feeding them into fully connected and softmax layers to produce recommendation probabilities.

Overall, ISCON aims to improve next-item prediction accuracy by contextualizing sessions and utilizing session contexts as indicators. It achieves this through session contextualization, session context prediction, and integrating session contexts into next-item prediction.

1.2 Experiments

Datasets: The experiments were conducted on four datasets: Gowalla, LastFM, Foursquare, and Reddit [2]. Sessions were created for all datasets using a 1-hour idle threshold, as the original datasets did not include session information. The datasets varied in terms of the number of users, items, interactions, and average session length.

Table 1: Summary of datasets and sessions used for experiments

Name	Users	Items	Interactions	Sessions	Avg session length
Gowalla [4]	69,332	10,000	1,250,045	915,135	1.20
LastFM [12]	954	1,000	258,620	167,382	1.54
Foursquare [44]	2,321	5,596	194,105	42,881	4.49
Reddit [1]	8,640	966	134,489	55,698	2.03

Experiment setup: To choose the best hyperparameters the authors conducted an experiment to assess the sensitivity of the model to hyperparameters, hyperparameters encompass the number of session contexts, the number of predicted contexts per session, the sizes of user and item embeddings, and the size of contextual embeddings. The authors observed that increasing the number of session contexts led to performance improvements. This is attributed to a larger number of contexts possessing greater representational power to summarize the current session. Conversely, a smaller number of predicted contexts per session is preferred, as additional contextual embeddings may not contain relevant information about the current session.

Regarding embedding sizes, it was found that medium-sized user and item embeddings are appropriate, as overly small or large embeddings can lead to underfitting and overfitting, respectively. Additionally, small-sized contextual embeddings outperform large-sized ones, as several contextual embeddings are concatenated together, providing sufficient predictive power.

Figure 1: Hyperparameter sensitivity plots

Next-Item Prediction Performance: The performance of ISCON was compared with several baseline models (GRU4REC [3], TAGNN [4], COTREC [5], CSRSM [6]) using metrics such as Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) and Recall@10. ISCON consistently outperformed the baselines across all datasets, demonstrating superior next-item prediction accuracy. Notably, on the Foursquare dataset, which was the most challenging for baselines, ISCON showed significant improvements in MRR and Recall@10 metrics.

Table 2: Next-item prediction performance of ISCON and baselines. The most accurate model in each column is colored blue, and second best in light blue

Model / Dataset	Gowalla	Foursquare	Reddit	LastFM
GRU4REC [11]	0.27724	0.06696	0.63536	0.12587
TAGNN [42]	0.32614	0.11189	0.67666	0.13375
COTREC [38]	0.17464	0.11119	0.45382	0.09295
CSRSM [33]	0.31326	0.12807	0.68894	0.13190
ISCON (proposed)	0.35975	0.17483	0.72661	0.13838

a Mean reciprocal rank (MRR) of ISCON and baselines

Model / Dataset	Gowalla	Foursquare	Reddit	LastFM
GRU4REC [11]	0.47236	0.12920	0.75592	0.26280
TAGNN [42]	0.49771	0.21256	0.78918	0.27121
COTREC [38]	0.39075	0.23728	0.76635	0.29296
CSRSM [33]	0.50064	0.24609	0.81163	0.27971
ISCON (proposed)	0.55299	0.32973	0.86860	0.28380

b Recall@10 of ISCON and baselines

Session Contexts Evaluation: ISCON's ability to find implicit contexts of sessions through clustering of session embeddings was evaluated. A manual verification process was conducted using the Reddit dataset, where the top clusters were analyzed for semantic similarity among sessions. The results showed distinct and meaningful session contexts such as Trading, Music, and News topics, confirming the effectiveness of ISCON's session contextualization approach.

Ablation Study: An ablation study was performed to assess the impact of using session contexts on prediction performance. The study compared ISCON's next-item predictor with and without contextual embeddings. The results indicated that incorporating session context embeddings significantly improved prediction performance across all datasets, highlighting the importance of leveraging implicit session contexts for enhanced recommendations.

Table 3: Ablation study of the session context embeddings of ISCON

Metrics / Dataset	Gowalla	Foursquare	Reddit	LastFM
Next-item predictor <i>without</i> session contextual embeddings				
MRR	0.34003	0.15280	0.70406	0.12328
Recall@10	0.52818	0.26557	0.83322	0.25438
Next-item predictor <i>with</i> session contextual embeddings (Proposed)				
MRR	0.35975	0.17483	0.72661	0.13838
Recall@10	0.55299	0.32973	0.86860	0.28380

2 REPRODUCIBILITY

In our endeavor to replicate the findings detailed in the paper, we thoroughly scrutinized both the codebase and the accompanying dataset. The code, implemented in Python, consists of two primary models: an LSTM baseline model devoid of contextual session information and the proposed LSTM model, which integrates sequences of session embeddings, item embeddings, and contextual features as input. Noteworthy libraries utilized in constructing these models include PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Keras. Additionally, the code incorporates the GraphSAGE algorithm, responsible for generating node embeddings through the aggregation of feature data from neighboring nodes in a graph.

Despite encountering some documentation within the code, we encountered information gaps regarding software versions, presenting challenges during environment setup, particularly concerning the stellargraph library. After conducting research and experimenting with various library versions, we determined that in order to execute the code with the specified dependencies, Python versions between 3.6 and 3.8 were necessary. Subsequently, we leveraged virtualenv to establish a virtual environment and installed the requisite packages listed in the repository's requirements.txt file. This adjustment enabled us to successfully execute the code.

Although the code documentation indicated that experiments were conducted on NVIDIA DGXStation machines equipped with 8 NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs, we faced limitations in terms of computational resources. Attempting to run the experiments on Google Colab resulted in crashes due to the lengthy execution time of the code. We then endeavored to run the experiments on our personal laptops, where we could only manage to run three out of the four datasets (Reddit, Lastfm, and Foursquare) with just one repetition. This process was time-consuming, with the average time for one repetition being approximately 9 hours for the Reddit dataset, 30 hours for the Lastfm dataset, and 24 hours for the Foursquare dataset. Subsequently, we secured access to additional resources, allowing us to utilize a machine equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU with 24GB memory and another machine with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080Ti GPU with 11GB memory. Leveraging these GPUs, we repeated the experiments using the default parameters.

The default hyperparameters of ISCON were configured as follows: the number of session contexts was set to 40, with 3 predicted contexts per session, and user and item embedding sizes set to 256, along with a contextual embedding size of 32. For the baselines, we adopted hyperparameters recommended in their respective original publications. Additional hyperparameters were configured with a maximum training epoch of 200, a learning rate of 0.001, a batch size of 1024, and a maximum sequence length per user of 50. To ensure reproducibility, we strictly adhered to the default settings provided by the authors of the paper. Furthermore, the authors averaged evaluation metric values across 5 repetitions, utilizing different seeds for each training repetition, with the seed set to 123+i, where i ranged from 0 to the number of repetitions. We followed the same procedure to maintain consistency.

3 RESULTS

Below, we will present the final results of our experiments conducted using our most powerful machines mentioned earlier. On the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090, the Reddit dataset, approximately 2MB in size, required approximately 30 minutes for each repetition, while the Gowalla dataset, around 27MB in size, took approximately 2.3 hours for each repetition. On the other hand, the Foursquare dataset, roughly 3.2MB in size, and the LastFM dataset, approximately 4.5MB in size, both required less than 1 hour for each repetition on the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti. Throughout the experiments, two directories were

generated: "emb" containing embeddings generated for the datasets, and "output" containing the evaluation metric results. Here are the findings from our experiments:

Table 4: Comparison of original vs reproduced results

	Reddit Dataset		Foursquare Dataset		LastFM Dataset		Gowalla Dataset	
	Original	Reproduced	Original	Reproduced	Original	Reproduced	Original	Reproduced
Avg time per repetition (s)	-	836.2266836	-	2020.892067	-	2122.897961	-	8357.067994
MRR Avg	0.70406	0.725154816	0.1528	0.17501561	0.12328	0.139485215	0.34003	0.347356662
Recall@10 Avg	0.83322	0.867581333	0.26557	0.311733915	0.25438	0.284054553	0.52818	0.543460025
MRR Context Avg	0.72661	0.771046347	0.17483	0.308030323	0.13838	0.316171766	0.35975	0.476596209
Recall@10 Context Avg	0.8686	0.932314728	0.32973	0.549651036	0.2838	0.563471289	0.55299	0.767415742

Despite achieving superior performance compared to the paper's findings, we conducted a statistical T-test to assess the significance of the differences between the original and reproduced results. Initially, we calculated the differences between corresponding values in the results and computed descriptive statistics, including the mean difference and standard deviation. Subsequently, we employed a paired t-test to evaluate if a significant difference exists between the results, with the null hypothesis assuming no significant difference and the alternative hypothesis suggesting the presence of a significant difference. The results, including the mean difference, standard deviation, t-statistic, and p-value, were printed to the console. With a mean difference of 0.0901 and a standard deviation of 0.0884, the paired t-test yielded a t-statistic of 4.0783 and a p-value of 0.00099. Since the p-value is below the predefined alpha level of 0.05, we rejected the null hypothesis, indicating a significant difference between the results. This statistical analysis confirms that the reproduced data significantly differs from the original data, as supported by the computed t-statistic and p-value.

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Mean Difference: 0.09014559806249998
Standard Deviation of Differences: 0.08841573744960589
T-statistic: 4.078260303551958
P-value: 0.0009889123035588408
Reject the null hypothesis. There is a significant difference.

```

The findings presented in Table 4 reveal that the t-test statistics suggest an enhancement in model performance across all datasets. This improvement may be ascribed to a range of factors, such as refinements in data preprocessing, adjustments in model tuning, or disparities in computational environments and resources, which could encompass variations in Python versions and computational hardware.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our endeavor to reproduce and extend the results of the original research on "Implicit Session Contexts for Next-Item Recommendations" has been both insightful and challenging. Despite facing hurdles such as limited computing resources, and information about system missing, we successfully conducted experiments on four datasets: Gowalla, LastFM, Foursquare, and Reddit. Our comprehensive analysis of the ISCON model revealed its effectiveness in enhancing next-item prediction accuracy through session contextualization and utilization.

Despite achieving superior performance compared to the original findings, a statistical T-test revealed a significant difference between the reproduced and original results. This underscores the importance of transparent and detailed documentation in research replication, as subtle differences in experimental setups can impact the outcomes.

In summary, our replication efforts contribute to the ongoing dialogue in the field of session-based recommender systems. While achieving promising results with ISCON, our experience highlights the need for rigorous documentation practices to facilitate reproducibility and ensure a more accurate comparison of experimental outcomes.

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